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How Are Performance Issues Caused and Resolved? — An Empirical Study from a Design Perspective

2-Min Teaser at ACM/SPEC ICPE 2020

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1. We investigated 192 real-life performance issues from *Apache Community*.

2. We categorized 8 recurring root causes and resolutions and performed an extensive literature review.

- Inefficient Data Structure (IDS)
- Inefficiency under Special Cases (ISC)
- Inefficient API Usage (IAU)
- Multi-threaded Blocking (MTB)
- Repeated Computation (RC)
- Inefficient Iteration (II)
- Redundant Data Processing (RDP)
- General Inefficient Algorithm (GIA)

4. Localized optimizations have slightly higher ROI; Design-level optimizations reflect trade-offs for other qualities.

3. 33% of the studied issues require design-level optimization, manifested in four typical patterns.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1 BlockingBinaryEncoder	(1)	-Ext, -dp	+Ext,+dp							
2 BinaryEncoder		(2)								
3 BufferedBinaryEncoder			+Ext	(3)						
4 DirectBinaryEncoder				+Ext	(4)					
5 EncoderFactory		+dp	+dp		+dp	+dp	(5)			
6 RpcSendTool						+dp	(6)			
7 RpcReceiveTool							+dp	(7)		
8 BinaryFragmentToJsonTool								+dp	(8)	
9 DataFileReadTool									+dp	(9)
10 JsonToBinaryFragmentTool										+dp

(a) Classic Design Pattern

	1	2	3	4
1 Matrix(*)	(1)			
2 TextPosition	dp	(2)		
3 PDFStreamEngine	dp	dp	(3)	
4 ShowTextGlyph	dp			(4)

	1	2	3
1 NumberFormatUtil	(1)		
2 PDAbstractContentStream(*)		+dp	(2)
3 PDContentStream			ext (3)

(b) Type I and Type II Propagation

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1 PDTrueTypeFont	(1)						
2 PDType1CFont		(2)					
3 PDType0Font			(3)				
4 PDType1Font				(4)			
5 PDType3Font					(5)		
6 PDCIDFontType0						dp	(6)
7 PDCIDFontType2							dp

(c) Optimization Clone

	1	2	3	4	5
1 PDFont	(1)				
2 PDSimpleFont		Ext	(2)		
3 COSNumber				(3)	
4 ICU4JImpl					(4)
5 PDFStreamEngine					

(d) Parallel Optimization